

Milestone:

MS39 - Video for healthcare professionals developed in English produced with guidance for NMG on how to adapt it to local languages

Lead Participant:

ELIXIR Hub

Author:

Zippy Tseng (ELIXIR Hub)

Due:

April 2024

Date Of Completion:

February 2026

Means of Verification

A video about 1+MG initiative and GDI for the healthcare professional.

Please see the link here for the video **"1+ Million Genomes Shaping the Future of Patient Care"**:

<https://vimeo.com/indiepicsclient/review/1058274987/da706dccd7>

Additional video on 1+MG introduction **"What is the 1+Million Genomes Initiative?"**:

<https://vimeo.com/indiepicsclient/review/1058275414/2e6234d5b5>

Milestone Delayed (if yes, please explain)

The video was delayed in order to include outputs of the project to provide a more comprehensive introduction of the project to the viewers.

Project participants & others

Zippy Tseng (ELIXIR Hub)

Elaine Harrison (ELIXIR Hub)

Serena Scollen (ELIXIR Hub)

Next action steps

Once approved by the GDI Management Board, the video production company will do final steps on purchasing stock footage, colour grading and sound mixing. The video will be uploaded to the ELIXIR YouTube channel along with two other videos under a dedicated playlist.

A news release and a series of social media posts will be published.

The videos will be shared with GDI project partners and NMG. The NMG should provide translation of subtitles to add on YouTube videos.

